

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISATION OF NEWER
COUMARIN DERIVATIVES AS ANTIBACTERIAL
ACTIVITY**¹Amit A. Jadhav, ²Dr. Kishorkumar B. Burade, ³Dr. Rita D. Chakole.¹At post. Avalai, Tal. Atpadi, Dist. Sangli. amitjadhav10397@gmail.com 9503061463.
Government College of Pharmacy, Karad.²At post. Karad, Vidyanagar saidapur. Government College of Pharmacy, Karad.³At post. Karad, Vidyanagar saidapur. Government College of Pharmacy, Karad.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Synthesis of new antimicrobial drugs is the need of current era. This is because of drug resistance of bacteria towards newly developed antibacterial, bacteria develop resistance like mutation, natural resistance, acquired resistance. so in this paper new coumarin derivatives were synthesized, characterized & checked for antibacterial activity for (Staphylococcus aureus, bacillus subtilis, Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa). Synthesized compounds shown antibacterial activity. This can be done through disk diffusion method, & checked zone of inhibition. In this synthesis process simple acetylation like reaction were used.

Key words: antibacterial, resistance, diffusion, zone of inhibition.

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Please cite this article in press Amit A. Jadhav et al, *Synthesis And Characterization Of Newer Coumarin Derivatives As Antibacterial Activity.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Coumarin (2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones) is a oxygen containing fused heterocycles used in drugs and dyes (1). Coumarin is a major class of naturally occurring compound. However, the plant kingdom constitutes a source of new chemicals, which may be important for their potential use in medicine. (3). They are the family of lactones containing benzpyran skeletal framework that have enjoyed isolation from plant as well as total synthesis in the laboratory (4). Incorporation of diff. functional groups into parent molecule it changes properties of parent compound & convert it into more useful content. Different heterocycles are important for antimicrobial activity, these changes potency, lipophilicity, polarity. N2, O2, S, containing heterocycles have great work in chemistry, it gives different activities like antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer. Coumarin reported as antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-tumor, antioxidant, anti-viral and anti-bacterial.(4). One heterocycle coupled with another it enhance the biological activity. Coumarin are the flavonoids as a core unit & isolated from natural sources & shows different biological properties. (6) (2)

Drug resistance

Because of drug resistance there is increased problem in infections produced by bacteria, fungi, virus. Hence development & discovery of useful anti-bacterial & fungal drug with novel MOA. Thus it becomes urgent task for infection Disease research program, to develop new antimicrobials. (8) Pathogens have evolved several mechanisms to neutralize antibiotics. (7) (19)

MATERIAL & METHODS:**Chemicals and instruments required**

Synthetic / analytical grade chemicals were used i.e. Resorcinol, Ethyl acetoacetate, Conc. H₂SO₄, Conc. HNO₃,

Iron powder, conc. HCl, Pyridine, NaOH, acetic anhydride, 4-bromo benzaldehyde, chloroacetic chloride, Benzoyl chloride, 3,5 dinitro benzoyl chloride.

Melting points were determined in open capillaries, using Boitus melting point apparatus. IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on Shimadzu IR

Affinity FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr discs and the values are expressed in cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra of compounds were recorded on Bruker Avance Ii 400 MHz NMR spectrophotometer using DMSO/CDC13 as an internal standard and the values are expressed in δ ppm. The elemental analyses of the compounds were recorded on Elemental Vario El Iii, Carlo Erba 1108 Elemental analyzer. The structures were confirmed by spectral and elemental analysis. (18)

General procedure for Synthesis**Synthesis of 4 methyl, 7 hydroxy coumarin**

Take 75 ml. of conc. H₂SO₄ in a 500 ml beaker, stirred in external ice water cooling until the Temp^f. of acid become about 5 °c – 10 °c. 18.5 gm of resorcinol added to 22.5 ml. of ethyl acetoacetate until a complete solⁿ. was obtained. Then this solⁿ. was added slowly to H₂SO₄. In such a way that the Temp^f. does not rise above 10 °c & continued stirring for ½ an hr. The mix. is poured into the ice/cold water & the solid product is separated, filtered out and dried. Then crude product was recrystallized from ethanol. The resultant Yields: 83.05%, Melting point: 190 OC, Molecular Formula: C₁₀H₈O₃, Molecular Mass: 176.16 and Solubility: Methanol, Ethanol, Pyridine, H₂SO₄ etc.(9) (20)

Synthesis of 4 methyl 7 ethanoate coumarin (A)

Take 2 ml of pyridine in 100 ml beaker in which add 1.76 g of 4 methyl 7 hydroxy coumarin, dissolve completely then add 1.10 ml of acetic anhydride. Stir it for upto product does not obtaine. Wash with water. Solid product collect & dry.

Synthesi of 4 methyl 7 benzoate coumarin (B)

Make (10 % w/v) NaOH sol. 30 ml in add 2 g of 4 methyl 7 hydroxy coumarin mix it well in conical flask then add 4 ml of benzoyl chloride, close flask with . Shake vigorously 15-20 min. collect product, wash with water & recrystallize by alcohol.

Synthesis of 4 methyl 7 chloroacetate coumarin (C)

Take pyridine: ether (2:1) in beaker add 2 g of 4 methyl 7 hydroxy coumarin, dissolve completely. Add 3 ml of chloroacetyl chloride, mix it well & collect solid product, wash it with water.

Scheme of Synthesis:**Fig.2 Scheme for R groups
Table no.1. Probable R groups.**

4 Methyl 7 Hydroxy coumarin	Compound		R
	A		COCH ₃
	B		COC ₆ H ₅
	C		COCH ₂ Cl

Mechanism of reaction:

IUPAC NAME: 4 Methyl, 7 hydroxy- 2H- chromen-2-one

C₁₀H₈O₃, Yellowish power (29.6 g, 83.05% yield), m.p 185-190 °C, λ max. (EtOH) 221 nm, R_f 0.6, IR (v, cm⁻¹): 3369.16 (OH str.), 1750 (C=O str.), 3010 (=C-H str.), 1669 (C=C str.), 1267 (C-O str. Ester)

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm: 7.8 (s, 1H, Ar H), 7.6 (d, 1H, Ar H), 7.3 (d, 1H, Ar H), 6.3 (s, 1H =CH), 2.35 (s, 3H, Ar CH₃).

Compound A-

IUPAC NAME: 4 Methyl, 7 acetoxy- 2H- chromen-2-one

C₁₃H₁₄O₄, Brownish powder (0.753g, 32.04% yield), m.p 132-138 °C, λ max (EtOH) 253 nm, R_f 0.7, IR (v, cm⁻¹): 1770 (C=O str.), 3036 (=C-H str.), 1640 (C=C str.), 1315 (C-O str.)

¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 7.9 (s, 1H, Ar H), 7.7 (d, 1H, Ar H), 7.5 (d, 1H, Ar H), 6.5 (s, 1H =CH), 2.35 (s, 3H, Ar CH₃). 2.1 (s, 1H COCH₃)

Compound B –

IUPAC NAME: 4 methyl, 7 benzoate- 2H- chromen-2-one

C₁₈H₁₇O₄, Whitish brown powder (2.8 g, 96.43% yield), m.p 90-95 °C, λ max (EtOH) 270 nm, R_f 0.8, IR (v, cm⁻¹): 1760 (C=O str.), 3010 (=C-H str.), 1668 (C=C str.), 1325 (C-O str.)

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm: 6.5-7.9 (s, 1H, Ar H), (d, 1H, Ar H), (d, 1H, Ar H), (s, 1H =CH), 2.35 (s, 3H, Ar CH₃) . 2.1 (s, 1H COCH₃)

Compound C –

IUPAC NAME: 4 methyl, 7 chloroacetoxy - 2H- chromen-2-one

C₁₃H₁₃O₄Cl, Whitish brown (1 g, 36.10 % yield), m.p 150-155 °C, λ max (MeOH) 250 nm, R_f 0.6, IR (v, cm⁻¹): 1723 (C=O str.), 3081 (=C-H str.), 1612 (C=C str.), 1312 (C-O str.), 852 (C-Cl str.)

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm: 6.5-8.0 (s, 1H, Ar H), (d, 1H, Ar H), (d, 1H, Ar H), (s, 1H =CH), 2.39 (s, 3H, Ar CH₃), 2.25 (s, 1H COCH₃) 4.1 (CH-Cl)

Antibacterial activity:

Antibacterial activity checked against gram positive (Staphylococcus aureus, bacillus subtilis) and Gram-negative bacteria (Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa)

This can be checked with disk diffusion method, in this bacterium grow on agar plate then disk deposited with sample to be tested kept it 24 hr. then check zone of inhibition, i.e. no growth occur at where sample present. Measured zone of inhibition with caliper (mm). Ciprofloxacin were used as standard antibacterial drug. All compounds were screened for antimicrobial activity & found to exhibit significant activity. Samples are made in DMSO as a solvent. Below table shows antibacterial activity of synthesized compounds compared to ciprofloxacin as a reference drug.(11) (14) (16).

Table no. 2. Antibacterial activity of synthesized compounds.

Compound	Zone of inhibition (mm)			
	Gram positive		Gram negative	
	S. aureus	B. subtilis	E. coli	Ps. aeruginosa
A	10	9	11	9
B	9	8	9	7
C	5	6	9	6
Ciprofloxacin	20	18	21	19
Ampicillin	17	23	18	22

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, we have prepared simple synthesis of substituted coumarins. The result of present study indicates that synthesized Compounds possess favourable antibacterial activity, that can be detected by comparing compounds activity with standards. It also requires further study to state molecular mechanisms, responsible for these biological activities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We gratefully acknowledge the whole support from government College Of pharmacy, Karad.

REFERENCES:

- Rajasekaran S, Rao G.K., Pai S.P.N. Ranjan A (2011), International journal of chem tech research,3(2),555-559
- Introduction to Coumarin and SAR Santhosh Penta Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India 1-8
- Antibacterial Activity of Coumarins Simone M. de Souzaa, Franco Delle Monacheb, and Artur Sma`nia Jr.a, a Departamento de Microbiologia e Parasitologia, Z. Naturforsch. 60c, 693D700 (2005); received February 22/April 18, 2005
- Olayinka A.O., Obinna N.C.,(2010) Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry, , 47,179-187.
- Synthesis of substituted Coumarin derivatives and their spectral Characterization Neha Mishra, Vrushali Patil, Ashish Asrondkar, A.S Bobade, Abhay Chowdhary 1Department of Chemotherapy, Haffkine Institute for Training, Research and Testing, India IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry (IOSR-JAC) e-ISSN: 2278-5736. Volume 7, Issue 8 Ver. II. (Aug. 2014), PP 48-51
- Design and synthesis of some amino coumarin derivatives by using mild catalyst Kadlag A. G.p.n 86-90 Department of Chemistry, S. N. Arts, D. J. M. Commerce and B. N. S. Science College, Sangamner
- The hunt for new antibiotics grows harder as resistance builds by Megha Satyanarayana DECEMBER 16, 2018 | APPEARED IN VOLUME 96, ISSUE 49
- Essentials of medical pharmacology 6th edition, KD Tripathi, JP publication. P.no. 667-681
- Synthesis of novel coumarin derivatives and its biological evaluations Swayam Sourav Sahoo1, Smita Shukla2, Subhangankar Nandy3* and Himanshu Bhusan Sahoo31Department of Pharma. Chemistry, Roland Institute of Pharma. Sciences, Berhampur, Orissa, India Pelagia Research Library European Journal of Experimental Biology, 2012, 2 (4):899-908
- Coumarins: The Antimicrobial agents Yasameen K. Al-Majedy,1,2 Abdul Amir H. Kadhum1, Ahmed A. Al-Amiry*1,2, Abu Bakar Mohamad1 1Department of Chemical and Process Engineering, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), Bangi, Selangor 43000, MALAYSIA. 2University of Technology (UOT), Baghdad 10001, IRAQ.
- Rapid antibiotic assay methods using bacillus stearothermophilus1 r. T. Igarashi, r. W. Baughman,F. E. Nelson2• 3• 5, and p. A. Hartifan2• 3 iowa state university of science and technology, ames (received for publication november 13, 1960)
- Antibacterial Activity of Simple Coumarins: Structural Requirements for Biological Activity Oliver Kayser and H erbert Kolodziej Institut für Pharmazie II, Pharmazeutische Biologie. Freie Universität Berlin, Königin-Luise-Str. 2+4, D-14195 Berlin, Germany Z. Naturforsch. 54c, 169-174 (1999); received November 11/December 8, 1998

13. Recent advances in 4-hydroxycoumarin chemistry. Part 1: Synthesis and reactions Moaz M. Abdou a,c,* , Rasha A. El-Saeed b, Samir Bondock b The Institute of Scientific and Industrial Research, Osaka University, 8-1 Mihogaoka, Ibaraki-shi, Osaka 567-0047, Japan
14. Rajasekaran S, Rao G.K., Pai S.P.N. Ranjan A, design and synthesis of some amino coumarin derivatives by using mild catalyst, International journal of chem tech research, (2011), 3(2),555-559.
15. Mounyr BalouiriMoulay SadikiSaad Koraichi Ibsouda. Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis 6 (2016) 71-79
16. SHRIRAM BAIIRAGI, ASHOK BHOSALE and MEENAKSHI N DEODHAR. Design, Synthesis and Evaluation of Schiff's Bases of 4-Chloro-3-coumarin aldehyde as Antimicrobial Agents. E-Journal of Chemistry <http://www.e-journals.net> 2009, 6(3), 759-762.
17. Cleidson Valgas, Simone Machado de Souza, Elza F A Smânia, screening methods to determine antibacterial activity of natural products Brazilian Journal of Microbiology (2007) 38:369-380
18. S. S. Ali, A. Kadi, I. A. Hashmi & S. W. Ng Synthesis of Some New Heterocyclic Compounds Derived from 3-Formylchromones and Their Antimicrobial Evaluation *Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds* volume 49, (2014) pages 1723–1731
19. Antibiotics: MedlinePlus". nih.gov. Retrieved 19 July 2016.
20. Kokila A. Parmer, Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of 2-(4-methyl -7-hydroxy-coumarin)-4-(cyclohexylamino)-6-(arylamino)-s-triazine . *Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 2013, 5 (1):24-27.
21. Maria João Matos, Lourdes Santana, Eugenio Uriarte, Orlando A. Abreu, Enrique Molina and Estela Guardado Yordi, "Coumarins — An Important Class of Phytochemicals", *INTCH*, 2015, 113-130.
22. Setarehsa betpoorand Farhad Hatamjafari "Synthesis of Coumarin Derivatives using Glutamic Acid under Solvent-free Conditions" , *ORIENTAL JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY*, 2014, Vol. 30, No. (2): Pg. 863-865
23. Korry Barnes, "What is Coumarin? - Structure, Synthesis & Derivatives"